

Constructing and Validating a Multidimensional Model of Students' Statistical Disposition in Indonesian Higher Education

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Abstract

Background: Statistical disposition significantly influences students' attitudes, beliefs, and behaviours toward learning statistics. Given the increasing demand for statistical literacy in our data-driven society, there is a growing need for a valid and reliable framework to measure this construct. However, comprehensive empirical models, especially in the Indonesian higher education context, are still limited.

Objective: This study aims to theoretically construct and empirically validate a dimensional model along with its indicators to measure students' statistical disposition in higher education settings.

Methodology: A quantitative approach was adopted using the descriptive method and cross-sectional survey design. Participants included undergraduate, master's, and doctoral students from a state university in Indonesia. Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) was employed to examine model fit and validate the constructs.

Results: The initial model with seven dimensions and nine indicators (two adapted from prior studies) failed to meet the acceptable fit criteria. After six iterative modifications, the final model, comprising six dimensions and thirteen indicators, showed good model fit and statistical validity.

Conclusion: The validated model offers a theoretically sound and empirically supported framework for assessing statistical disposition among university students, contributing to enhanced evaluation and understanding in the field of statistics education.

Unique Contribution: This study presents one of the first empirically validated multidimensional models of statistical disposition tailored for Indonesian higher education, filling a notable gap in international statistics education research.

Key Recommendation: Educators and curriculum developers should integrate the validated model into teaching strategies and assessment tools to foster students' positive dispositions toward learning statistics and support ongoing educational improvements.

Keywords: Statistical disposition; statistics education; higher education; confirmatory factor analysis; measurement model.

Introduction

Many students encounter difficulties in learning statistics (Bromage et al., 2022), and these challenges do not stem solely from cognitive factors. Non-cognitive factors like negative attitudes and misconceptions also significantly impact learning (Gal & Ginsburg, 1994). These affective elements can substantially hinder students' ability to comprehend statistical concepts, limit the application of statistical knowledge in real-world contexts, and ultimately reduce their engagement in statistics learning. Given these challenges, educators must assess and monitor students' feelings and dispositions toward statistics to create a more positive learning environment (Aty et al., 2025).

Disposition has long been recognised as critical in educational theory (Altan et al., 2019). Disposition is defined as a habit of mind (Altan et al., 2019), a relatively stable behavioural tendency, or a cognitive-affective sensitivity that shapes individual responses across various contexts (Perkins et al., 2018; Sudirman et al., 2024). It relates to stable personality traits that influence behaviour across different contexts (Michael et al., 2025; Wafa, 2024). Moreover, personality traits and dispositions can be operationalised and measured through validated instruments employing psychometric approaches such as factor analysis.

In statistics education, Pfannkuch and Wild (2000) introduced statistical disposition as one of the four central components of statistical thinking, alongside investigation, representation, and reasoning. Although this framework has made a significant conceptual contribution, its development of statistical disposition was based on qualitative interviews with experts and lacked psychometric validation. This raises questions about the nature of the construct, whether statistical disposition represents a stable and measurable personality trait or merely reflects temporary and context-dependent behavioural responses. Due to this ambiguity, statistical disposition lacks empirical validation as a measurable construct in educational assessment.

Established theories of thinking hold that dispositions are essential to cognitive engagement and decision-making (Perkins et al., 2018). In educational psychology, learning is often conceptualised as the development of dispositions, tendencies to think or act in particular ways in response to specific situations. Productive dispositions in statistics, such as curiosity, persistence, and scepticism, are deemed crucial for nurturing students' statistical thinking and reasoning skills

(Pfannkuch & Wild, 2000). Furthermore, positive dispositions promote statistical literacy and enhance students' ability to analyse data-driven claims encountered in everyday life critically.

Despite the recognised importance of disposition in statistics education, empirical research on statistical disposition remains scarce, particularly in non-Western contexts. Gal and Ginsburg (1994) emphasised that dispositional aspects, including attitudes, beliefs, and affect, are vital yet underexplored dimensions in statistics education. While international literature, such as Garfield and Chance (2000), touches on innovative assessment practices in statistics education, it does not explicitly develop or validate instruments to reliably measure students' statistical dispositions. In the Indonesian context, empirical studies on this issue are still limited. Martadiputra (2012) found significant improvements in students' statistical dispositions following modified MEAs instruction. Conversely, Martadiputra (2012) reported persistently low levels of statistical disposition despite a semester of instruction, highlighting the challenges in shifting affective responses. Cho et al. (2025) also identified a relationship between statistical literacy and disposition. However, these studies have yet to develop theoretical models or empirically validate the dimensions and indicators of statistical disposition using rigorous psychometric methods. This indicates a persistent gap in the development of systematic and applicable measurement models for statistical disposition in higher education settings in Indonesia.

In light of this research gap, the present study seeks to make substantial contributions in three key areas: (1) designing an instrument to measure university students' statistical dispositions based on theoretically defined dimensions and indicators; (2) constructing and validating a theoretical model of statistical disposition using Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA); and (3) refining the model to obtain a final structure that meets established model fit criteria. The primary contribution of this study is the development of a psychometrically validated instrument for assessing statistical disposition, thereby addressing the paucity of research, both globally and nationally, on affective measurement in statistics education. Additionally, this research strengthens the theoretical foundation regarding the role of disposition in learning statistics, particularly in how affective dimensions interact with students' learning outcomes. Furthermore, the study proposes a practical assessment framework that educators and curriculum designers can utilise to identify affective barriers among students and develop pedagogical strategies that support the cultivation of positive dispositions toward statistics in higher education.

Methodology

Research Design

This study used a descriptive quantitative design with a cross-sectional approach to investigate the latent construct of students' statistical disposition across different levels of higher education. A quantitative approach was selected because this study aimed to measure psychological attributes, such as attitudes, beliefs, and affective tendencies, using psychometrically validated indicators (Strunk & Mwavita, 2024). The quantitative approach was used to systematically describe students' statistical disposition without manipulating the variables involved. A cross-sectional design was chosen because data were collected at a single point in time from a sample of undergraduate, master's, and doctoral students currently enrolled in statistics courses (Leavy et al., 2017). This design allowed examination of variations in statistical disposition across educational

levels within one academic term, offering a comprehensive snapshot of affective factors potentially influencing learning outcomes. The choice of this design was also guided by practical considerations, including time constraints and participant availability, while still allowing for meaningful inferential analysis based on students’ demographic and academic characteristics.

Research Sample

The participants of this study were selected using a purposeful sampling approach (Leavy et al., 2017), namely, every undergraduate, master's, or doctoral student who was enrolled in a statistics lecture taught by the researcher at a public university in Bandung, West Java Province, Indonesia, during the odd and even semesters of the 2023/2024 academic year. The total sample consisted of 126 students, comprising 38.10% undergraduate, 48.41% postgraduate, and 13.49% doctoral students, drawn from 11 study programs. All participants were attending one of the seven statistics courses taught by the researcher (See Table 1).

Although this sample was limited to a single institution, including students from diverse academic levels and study programs provided variation in learning backgrounds and experiences, thereby strengthening the robustness of the findings. Moreover, the adequacy of the sample size for factor analysis was confirmed through the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) test and Bartlett’s Test of Sphericity, both of which met recommended thresholds (Huck, 2012; Sarmiento & Costa, 2019). The Measure of Sampling Adequacy (MSA) values for all 29 indicators exceeded 0.500, further supporting the suitability of the data for Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) and Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA).

Table 1: Characteristics of the Research Sample

No.	Study program	Course	Many people	%	Level	
					Many people	%
1	Bachelor of International Program Science Education	SE312 Statistics	17	13.49	48	38.10
2	Bachelor of Mathematics Education	MT325 Research Data Analysis	31	24.60		
3	Master of Indonesian Language for Foreign Speakers	PS701 Applied Statistics	3	2.38		
4	Master of Sports Management & Master of Physical Education Sports	PS701 Applied Statistics	22	17.46		
5	Master of Indonesian Language Education	PS701 Applied Statistics	10	7.94	61	48.41
6	Master of Education in Mathematics	MT795 Research Data Analysis	3	2.38		
7	Master of Sports Coaching Education	PS701 Applied Statistics	13	10.32		
8	Master of Sports Education	PS701 Applied Statistics	10	7.94		

No.	Study program	Course	Many people	%	Level	
					Many people	%
9	Doctor of Mathematics Education	MT834 Quantitative Research Methods in Mathematics Education	3	2.38	17	13.49
10	Doctor of Sport Education by Research	PS801 Science Data Analysis	2	1.59		
11	Doctor of Sports Education Regular	PS801 Science Data Analysis	12	9.52		
Total			126	100.00	126	100.00

Research Instruments

Data on students' statistical disposition were collected using a researcher-developed rating scale based on the theoretical study's results. Theoretically, students' statistical disposition consists of seven dimensions and twenty-eight indicators, namely: Statistical disposition consists of seven dimensions, namely: 1) seriousness in learning (X_1) indicators: interest in lectures (X_{11}), punctual attendance in lectures (X_{12}), desire to do assignments (X_{13}), collecting assignments (X_{14}), activeness in attending lectures (X_{15}), and seriousness in attending lectures (X_{16}) (Gal & Ginsburg, 1994; Perkins et al., 2018); 2) self-confidence (X_2) indicators: confidence in asking questions (X_{21}), confidence in answering questions (X_{22}), confidence in communicating ideas (X_{23}), confidence in solving problems (X_{24}), and confidence in using statistics (X_{25}) (Gal & Ginsburg, 1994; Perkins et al., 2018); 3) Flexibility in exploring ideas and alternative problem solving (X_3) indicators: flexibility in exploring statistical ideas (X_{31}), and) flexibility in finding alternative solutions to statistical problems (X_{32}) (Perkins et al., 2018); 4) Persistence in facing and solving problems (X_4), indicators: persistence in facing statistical problems (X_{41}), persistence in solving statistical problems (X_{42}), persistence in understanding the problem (X_{43}), persistence in understanding the procedure (X_{44}), persistence in understanding the concept (X_{45}), and persistence in understanding other important aspects of statistics (X_{46}) (Perkins et al., 2018); 5) Monitoring and reflecting on thinking (X_5), indicators are: the ability to pay attention to the ideas and statistical thinking put forward by lecturers and or students (X_{51}), the ability to pay attention to the ideas and statistical thinking put forward by students (X_{52}), the desire to respond to other people's ideas and statistical thinking based on one's own thinking (X_{53}) (Perkins et al., 2018); 6) High curiosity (X_6) indicators: the desire to solve new challenging problems (X_{61}), the desire to study the material to be lectured on their own (X_{62}), the desire to have other reading sources besides those required by the lecturer (X_{63}); and the desire to learn non-routine things (X_{64}), the desire to ask non-routine things (X_{65}) (Perkins et al., 2018); and 7) Sharing opinions with others (X_7), indicators are: the desire to share opinions, ideas, and ideas with lecturers (X_{71}), and the desire to share opinions, ideas, and ideas with fellow students (X_{72}).

The rating scale was developed using an 11-point format arranged sequentially (Krosnick et al., 2005) from left to right, ranging from 0 to 10 points, with an extended rating scale to produce more accurate responses (Krosnick et al., 2005). A marked increase in item reliability occurs when

moving from a 2-point scale to a 7-point scale, up to 11 points in length. Item validity also increases as the scale lengthens from 2 points.

An example of a Rating Scale developed for the dimension of seriousness in learning, which has six indicators, can be seen is > 0.500 in Table 2.

Table 2: Example of Rating Scale Developed

Statistical Disposition			Scale										
No.	Dimension/Indicator		0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
A.	Seriousness in learning												
1.	Interest in lectures												
2.	Attendance in lectures												
3.	Intention to do assignments												
4.	Collecting assignments												
5.	Activeness in lectures												
6.	Seriousness in attending lectures												

The results of the validity test of the statistical disposition rating scale items are presented in Table 3 below.

Table 3: Validity Test Results of Students' Statistical Disposition Rating Scale Items

Variable	Magnitude	Value	Variable	Magnitude	Value	Variable	Magnitude	Value
X ₁₁	Pearson Correlation	.708**	X ₂₅	Pearson Correlation	.674**	X ₅₂	Pearson Correlation	.749**
	Sig. (1-tailed)	0.000		Sig. (1-tailed)	0.000		Sig. (1-tailed)	0.000
	N	126		N	126		N	126
X ₁₂	Pearson Correlation	.299**	X ₃₁	Pearson Correlation	.753**	X ₅₃	Pearson Correlation	.774**
	Sig. (1-tailed)	0.000		Sig. (1-tailed)	0.000		Sig. (1-tailed)	0.000
	N	126		N	126		N	126
X ₁₃	Pearson Correlation	.670**	X ₃₂	Pearson Correlation	.764**	X ₆₁	Pearson Correlation	.703**
	Sig. (1-tailed)	0.000		Sig. (1-tailed)	0.000		Sig. (1-tailed)	0.000
	N	126		N	126		N	126
X ₁₄	Pearson Correlation	.411**	X ₄₁	Pearson Correlation	.768**	X ₆₂	Pearson Correlation	.705**
	Sig. (1-tailed)	0.000		Sig. (1-tailed)	0.000		Sig. (1-tailed)	0.000
	N	126		N	126		N	126
X ₁₅	Pearson Correlation	.689**	X ₄₂	Pearson Correlation	.814**	X ₆₃	Pearson Correlation	.627**
	Sig. (1-tailed)	0.000		Sig. (1-tailed)	0.000		Sig. (1-tailed)	0.000
	N	126		N	126		N	126
X ₁₆	Pearson Correlation	.624**	X ₄₃	Pearson Correlation	.785**	X ₆₄	Pearson Correlation	.668**
	Sig. (1-tailed)	0.000		Sig. (1-tailed)	0.000		Sig. (1-tailed)	0.000

Variable	Magnitude	Value	Variable	Magnitude	Value	Variable	Magnitude	Value
	N	126		N	126		N	126
X ₂₁	Pearson Correlation	.672**	X ₄₄	Pearson Correlation	.753**	X ₆₅	Pearson Correlation	.670**
	Sig. (1-tailed)	0.000		Sig. (1-tailed)	0.000		Sig. (1-tailed)	0.000
	N	126		N	126		N	126
X ₂₂	Pearson Correlation	.659**	X ₄₅	Pearson Correlation	.755**	X ₇₁	Pearson Correlation	.738**
	Sig. (1-tailed)	0.000		Sig. (1-tailed)	0.000		Sig. (1-tailed)	0.000
	N	126		N	126		N	126
X ₂₃	Pearson Correlation	.794**	X ₄₆	Pearson Correlation	.741**	X ₇₂	Pearson Correlation	.650**
	Sig. (1-tailed)	0.000		Sig. (1-tailed)	0.000		Sig. (1-tailed)	0.000
	N	126		N	126		N	126
X ₂₄	Pearson Correlation	.724**	X ₅₁	Pearson Correlation	.730**			
	Sig. (1-tailed)	0.000		Sig. (1-tailed)	0.000			
	N	126		N	126			

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (1-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (1-tailed).

From Table 3, it can be seen that the Sig. (1-tailed) for each statistical disposition rating scale item is smaller than the significance level $\alpha = 0.05$ with $N = 126$ so that all items of the developed students' statistical disposition rating scale are valid at the significance level $\alpha = 0.05$ with degrees of freedom $dk = 124$ because the Sig. (1-tailed) < 0.05 (Huck, 2012). Of the 29 valid items, it is known that there are 2 (6.90%) items that have low validity (Huck, 2012); 5 (17.24%) items that have moderate validity (Huck, 2012); and 22 (75.86%) items that have high validity (Huck, 2012).

Furthermore, the results of the statistical disposition rating scale instrument reliability test with the help of SPSS are shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Reliability Test Results of Statistical Disposition Rating Scale Instrument

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
0.961	0.961	29

Because the value of Cronbach's Alpha = 0.961 > 0.8 , the student's Statistical Disposition Rating Scale instrument developed is reliable, and the instrument's reliability coefficient > 0.9 is categorised as perfect (Sarmiento & Costa, 2019). Therefore, the Statistical Disposition Rating Scale instrument developed for students' CFA was used and demonstrated perfect reliability.

Data Analysis

This study employed two types of data analysis, namely Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) and Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA). EFA was conducted to identify the relationships among the manifest variables (indicators) of students' statistical disposition and to establish the initial dimensional structure within a Structural Equation Model (SEM). The analysis began with 29 indicators, which were grouped into seven dimensions of statistical disposition. In conducting EFA, two criteria were considered. First, sampling adequacy was tested using the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) measure and Bartlett's Test of Sphericity. A KMO value greater than 0.600 (Huck, 2012) and a significance value of Bartlett's Test below 0.05 indicated sample adequacy (Sarmiento & Costa, 2019). Second, communalities values for each item were assessed using the Anti-image Correlation (MSA), with values greater than 0.500 considered acceptable for subsequent CFA (Sarmiento & Costa, 2019).

CFA was then performed to verify and confirm the factor structure hypothesised from the EFA (Hair et al., 2012). CFA serves to determine how well a set of observed indicators represents the underlying latent constructs (satisfied the requirements) that cannot be measured directly. In this study, CFA was evaluated using six model fit indices, including Probability > 0.05 (Hair et al., 2013) students' statistical disposition, chi-square divided by degrees of freedom ($Cmin/df \leq 2.00$) (Schermelleh-Engel et al., 2003), RMSEA < 0.08 (Schermelleh-Engel et al., 2003), GFI ≥ 0.90 (Schermelleh-Engel et al., 2003), TLI ≥ 0.95 (Schermelleh-Engel et al., 2003), and CFI ≥ 0.95 (Schermelleh-Engel et al., 2003). If the initial model did not meet these indices, the modification process was conducted by eliminating indicators with the lowest factor loadings or Standardised Regression Weights below 0.700 (Hair et al., 2013).

The modification process was conducted iteratively from Model 1 through Model 6. Model-1 was modified by removing five indicators (X_{16} , X_{25} , X_{13} , X_{62} , and X_{46}), resulting in Model-2. Model-2 was then refined by removing three indicators (X_{11} , X_{63} , and X_{15}), producing Model-3. In Model-3, three additional indicators (X_{45} , X_{53} , and X_{24}) were removed, leading to Model-4. In Model-4, two indicators (X_{22} and X_{21}) were eliminated, yielding Model-5. Finally, in Model-5, one indicator (X_{44}) was removed, resulting in Model-6 as the final model. The final model (Model-6) consisted of six dimensions and thirteen indicators of students' statistical disposition. The fit indices demonstrated that this model met all recommended thresholds, with Probability = 0.268 (> 0.05), $Cmin/df = 1.115$ (< 2.00), RMSEA = 0.030 (< 0.08), GFI = 0.939 (≥ 0.90), TLI = 0.994 (≥ 0.95), and CFI = 0.996 (≥ 0.95). Thus, Model-6 was retained as the best-fitting model representing the dimensions and indicators of students' statistical disposition.

Results and Discussion

Broadly speaking, this paper presents two primary results of the data analysis: the findings from the Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) and the Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA), which together provide comprehensive insights into the underlying factor structure and the validity of the proposed measurement model.

EFA Results

EFA was conducted using IBM SPSS version 26. The EFA results are presented in Table 5.

Table 5: KMO and Bartlett’s Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.905
Bartlett’s Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	3196.871
	Df	406
	Sig.	.000

Table 5 shows the KMO value. Based on the results of the theoretical study, the researcher succeeded in developing $= 0.905 > 0.600$ and the Sig. Value for Bartlett’s test $= 0.000 < \alpha = 0.05$, so that the sample size used in the study, namely 126 students, has met the requirements for CFA (Sarmiento & Costa, 2019; Schermelleh-Engel et al., 2003).

Table 6: Anti-Image Correlation

Indicators	Anti-image Correlation	Indicators	Anti-image Correlation	Indicators	Anti-image Correlation
X ₁₁	.928 ^a	X ₂₅	.950 ^a	X ₅₂	.913 ^a
X ₁₂	.709 ^a	X ₃₁	.919 ^a	X ₅₃	.935 ^a
X ₁₃	.905 ^a	X ₃₂	.908 ^a	X ₆₁	.924 ^a
X ₁₄	.764 ^a	X ₄₁	.907 ^a	X ₆₂	.915 ^a
X ₁₅	.885 ^a	X ₄₂	.930 ^a	X ₆₃	.908 ^a
X ₁₆	.890 ^a	X ₄₃	.916 ^a	X ₆₄	.831 ^a
X ₂₁	.922 ^a	X ₄₄	.928 ^a	X ₆₅	.855 ^a
X ₂₂	.911 ^a	X ₄₅	.909 ^a	X ₇₁	.862 ^a
X ₂₃	.952 ^a	X ₄₆	.917 ^a	X ₇₂	.828 ^a
X ₂₄	.957 ^a	X ₅₁	.894 ^a		

a. Measures of Sampling Adequacy (MSA)

From Table 6, it is known that the MSA Anti-image Correlation value for each indicator is > 0.500 , so that all (29 pieces) indicators of students’ statistical disposition are eligible for CFA (Sarmiento & Costa, 2019).

Table 7: Communalities

Indicators	Initial	Extraction	Indicators	Initial	Extraction	Indicators	Initial	Extraction
X ₁₁	1.000	0.597	X ₂₅	1.000	0.704	X ₅₂	1.000	0.833
X ₁₂	1.000	0.677	X ₃₁	1.000	0.756	X ₅₃	1.000	0.797
X ₁₃	1.000	0.698	X ₃₂	1.000	0.772	X ₆₁	1.000	0.640
X ₁₄	1.000	0.795	X ₄₁	1.000	0.761	X ₆₂	1.000	0.768
X ₁₅	1.000	0.773	X ₄₂	1.000	0.863	X ₆₃	1.000	0.705
X ₁₆	1.000	0.674	X ₄₃	1.000	0.885	X ₆₄	1.000	0.860
X ₂₁	1.000	0.793	X ₄₄	1.000	0.798	X ₆₅	1.000	0.850
X ₂₂	1.000	0.752	X ₄₅	1.000	0.754	X ₇₁	1.000	0.904

X ₂₃	1.000	0.798	X ₄₆	1.000	0.687	X ₇₂	1.000	0.917
X ₂₄	1.000	0.700	X ₅₁	1.000	0.829			

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

From Table 7 Commuality, it is known that the extraction value for each indicator is > 0.500 so that all (29) indicators can be used to explain the dimensions of the statistical disposition of students (Sarmiento & Costa, 2019).

CFA Results

CFA was used to assess the accuracy of the students' statistical disposition model using the maximum likelihood method in IBM SPSS AMOS version 23. Based on the EFA results, the sampling adequacy measures based on KMO and Bartlett's test are satisfied. Furthermore, based on the MSA Anti-image Correlation value and the extraction value of Commuality, it is known that all (29) indicators and seven dimensions of students' statistical disposition are eligible for further analysis using CFA (Sarmiento & Costa, 2019; Huck, 2012; Hair et al., 2013).

1. Initial Model: All Dimensions and Indicators of Statistical Disposition are included in the Model

The results of data analysis with the help of IBM SPSS AMOS version 23 obtained the Initial-Model of students' statistical disposition with a fit index: 1) Probability = 0.000 (> 0.05 (Hair et al., 2013) is not satisfied); 2) Cmin/df = 2.206 (< 2.00 (Schermelleh-Engel et al., 2003) is not satisfied); 3) RMSEA = 0.098 (< 0.08 (Schermelleh-Engel et al., 2003) is not satisfied); 4) GFI = 0.708 (≥ 0.90 (Schermelleh-Engel et al., 2003) not satisfied); 5) TLI = 0.841 (Schermelleh-Engel et al., 2003) not satisfied); and 6) CGI = 0.861 (≥ 0.95 (Schermelleh-Engel et al., 2003) is not satisfied). So, the Initial-Model, as shown in Figure 1, cannot be used to model the dimensions and indicators of students' statistical disposition. Therefore, the Initial Model should be modified.

The initial model modification was carried out by eliminating indicators X₁₂, X₁₄, and X₆₁ because the loading factors, or the estimated values of the Standardised Regression Weights, for the three indicators were 0.318, 0.465, and 0.681, respectively, all of which were less than 0.7 (Schermelleh-Engel et al., 2003). The results of the modification of the initial model obtained Model-1, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Initial Model of Dimensions and Indicators of Students' Statistical Disposition

2. Model 1: Elimination of X₁₂ and X₁₄ from the Initial Model

The results of data analysis with the help of IBM SPSS AMOS version 23 obtained Model-1 dimensions and indicators of students' statistical disposition with fit indices: 1) Probability = 0.000 (> 0.05(Hair et al., 2013) is not satisfied); 2) Cmin/df = 2.183 (< 2.00 (Schermelleh-Engel et al., 2003) is not satisfied); 3) RMSEA = 0.097 (< 0.08 (Schermelleh-Engel et al., 2003) is not satisfied); 4) GFI = 0.736 (≥ 0.90 (Schermelleh-Engel et al., 2003) not satisfied); 5) TLI = 0.867 (≥ 0.95 (Schermelleh-Engel et al., 2003) not satisfied); and 6) CGI = 0.886 (≥ 0.95 (Schermelleh-Engel et al., 2003) is not satisfied). So, Model-1 as shown in Figure 2 cannot be used to model the dimensions and indicators of students' statistical disposition. Therefore, Model-1 must be modified.

Model-1 modification is done by eliminating indicators X₁₆, X₂₅, X₁₃, X₆₂, and X₄₆ because they have the smallest Standardised Regression Weights estimate values (Schermelleh-Engel et al., 2003) of 0.699, 0.702, 0.704, 0.728, and 0.730, respectively. The modification results of Model-1 obtained Model-2, as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Model-1 Dimensions and Indicators of Students' Statistical Disposition

3. Model 2: Elimination of X16, X25, X13, X62, and X46 from Model 1

The results of data analysis with the help of IBM SPSS AMOS version 23 obtained Model-2 dimensions and indicators of students' statistical disposition with fit indices: 1) Probability = 0.000 (> 0.05(Hair et al., 2013) is not satisfied); 2) Cmin/df = 2.081 (< 2.00 (Schermelleh-Engel et al., 2003) is not satisfied); 3) RMSEA = 0.093 (< 0.08 (Schermelleh-Engel et al., 2003) is not satisfied); 4) GFI = 0.801 (≥ 0.90 (Schermelleh-Engel et al., 2003) not satisfied); 5) TLI = 0.904 (≥ 0.95 (Schermelleh-Engel et al., 2003) not satisfied); and 6) CGI = 0.923 (≥ 0.95 (Schermelleh-Engel et al., 2003) is not satisfied). So, Model-2, as shown in Figure 3, cannot be used to model students' statistical disposition dimensions and indicators. Therefore, Model-2 must be modified.

Model-2 modification is achieved by eliminating indicators X11, X63, and X15 because the three indicators have the smallest Standardised Regression Weights estimates (Schermelleh-Engel et al., 2003), namely 0.691, 0.736, and 0.737. The modification results of Model-2 obtained Model-3, as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 3. Model-2 Dimensions and Indicators of Students' Statistical Disposition

4. Model-3: Elimination of X₁₁, X₆₃, and X₁₅ from Model 2

The results of data analysis with the help of IBM SPSS AMOS version 23 obtained Model-3 dimensions and indicators of students' statistical disposition with fit indices: 1) Probability = 0.000 (> 0.05(Hair et al., 2013) is not satisfied); 2) Cmin/df = 2.197 (< 2.00(Schermelleh-Engel et al., 2003) is not satisfied); 3) RMSEA = 0.098 (< 0.08 (Schermelleh-Engel et al., 2003) is not satisfied); 4) GFI = 0.823 (\geq 0.90 (Schermelleh-Engel et al., 2003) not satisfied); 5) TLI = 0.912 (\geq 0.95(Schermelleh-Engel et al., 2003) not satisfied); and 6) CGI = 0.931 (\geq 0.95(Schermelleh-Engel et al., 2003) is not satisfied). So, Model-3 as shown in Figure 4 cannot be used to model the dimensions and indicators of students' statistical disposition. Therefore, Model-3 must be modified.

Model-3 modification is done by eliminating indicators X₄₅, X₅₃, and X₂₄ because the three indicators have the smallest Standardized Regression Weights estimate values (Schermelleh-Engel et al., 2003), namely 0.762, 0.767, and 0.777. The modification results of Model-3 obtained Model-4, as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 4. Model-3 Dimensions and Indicators of Students' Statistical Disposition

5. Model 4: Elimination of X45, X53, and X24 from Model 3

The results of data analysis with the help of IBM SPSS AMOS version 23 obtained Model-4 dimensions and indicators of dimensions and indicators of students' statistical disposition with the fit index: 1) Probability = 0.002 (> 0.05(Hair et al., 2013) is not satisfied); 2) Cmin/df = 1.534 (< 2.00 (Schermelleh-Engel et al., 2003) is satisfied); 3) RMSEA = 0.065 (< 0.08 (Schermelleh-Engel et al., 2003) satisfied); 4) GFI = 0.894 (≥ 0.90 (Schermelleh-Engel et al., 2003) not satisfied); 5) TLI = 0.967 (≥ 0.95 (Schermelleh-Engel et al., 2003) satisfied); and 6) CGI = 0.976 (≥ 0.95 (Schermelleh-Engel et al., 2003) is satisfied). So, Model-4, as shown in Figure 5, cannot be used to model students' statistical disposition dimensions and indicators. Therefore, Model-4 must be modified.

The Model-4 modification is achieved by eliminating indicator X22, as the two indicators have the smallest Standardised Regression Weights estimates (Schermelleh-Engel et al., 2003), namely 0.775. The modification results of Model-4 obtained Model-5, as shown in Figure 6.

Figure 5. Model-4 Dimensions and Indicators of Students' Statistical Disposition

6. Model 5: Elimination of X22 and X21 from Model 4

The results of data analysis with the help of IBM SPSS AMOS version 23 obtained Model-5 dimensions and indicators of students' statistical disposition with fit indices: 1) Probability = 0.002 (> 0.05(Hair et al., 2013) is not satisfied); 2) Cmin/df = 1.401 (< 2.00 (Schermelleh-Engel et al., 2003) is satisfied); 3) RMSEA = 0.057 (< 0.08 (Schermelleh-Engel et al., 2003) is satisfied); 4) GFI = 0.910 (\geq 0.90 (Schermelleh-Engel et al., 2003) is satisfied); 5) TLI = 0.977 (\geq 0.95 (Schermelleh-Engel et al., 2003) is satisfied); and 6) CGI = 0.984 (\geq 0.95 (Schermelleh-Engel et al., 2003) is satisfied)). So, Model-5, as shown in Figure 6, cannot be used to model students' statistical disposition dimensions and indicators. Therefore, Model-5 should be modified.

The Model-5 modification is to eliminate the x44 indicator because it has the smallest Standardised Regression Weights estimate (Schermelleh-Engel et al., 2003), namely 0.829. The results of modifying Model-5 yielded Model-6, as shown in Figure 7.

Figure 6. Model-5 Dimensions and Indicators of Students' Statistical Disposition

7. Model-6: Elimination of X₄₄ from Model 5

The results of data analysis with the help of IBM SPSS AMOS version 23 obtained Model-5 dimensions and indicators of students' statistical disposition with fit indices: 1) Probability = 0.268 (> 0.05 (Hair et al., 2013) is satisfied); 2) Cmin/df = 1.115 (< 2.00 (Schermelleh-Engel et al., 2003) is satisfied); 3) RMSEA = 0.030 (< 0.08 (Schermelleh-Engel et al., 2003) satisfied); 4) GFI = 0.939 (≥ 0.90 (Schermelleh-Engel et al., 2003) satisfied); 5) TLI = 0.994 (≥ 0.95 (Schermelleh-Engel et al., 2003) satisfied); and 6) CGI = 0.996 (≥ 0.95 (Schermelleh-Engel et al., 2003) is satisfied). So, Model-6, as shown in Figure 7, can be used to model students' statistical disposition dimensions and indicators.

Figure 7. Model-6 Dimensions and Indicators of Students' Statistical Disposition

Discussion

Discussion of EFA Results

Based on EFA, a model can be constructed but there are no analytical procedure features that allow the model to be tested (Huck, 2012). Therefore, EFA will not work well if the sample size is small, so researchers must collect a sufficient amount of data (Hair et al., 2013). From the results of EFA using KMO and for Bartlett's test, it is known that the sample size used in the study, namely 126 students, has satisfied the requirements for CFA (Sarmento & Costa, 2019). The selected sample has also represented the level of education, namely 38.10% of undergraduate students, 48.41% of master students, and 13.49% of doctoral students. An overview of the sample characteristics can be seen in Figure 8.

Figure 8. Diagram of Sample Characteristics

The EFA results further show that all indicators have Anti-image Correlation values and Extraction Communalities values > 0.500 (Sarmiento & Costa, 2019) so that the 29 indicators and 7 dimensions can be included in the theoretical model of students' statistical disposition (Huck, 2012) which will be tested empirically using CFA (Sarmiento & Costa, 2019; Hair et al., 2013).

Discussion of CFA Results

Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) involves measured variables, an initial matrix of reciprocal relationships among these variables, factors, and factor loadings (Huck, 2012). CFA in this study was used for the purpose of assessing the construct validity of measurement instruments designed to measure students' statistical disposition. Through CFA, researchers empirically test the suitability of the theoretical model of statistical disposition presented in structural equation modelling (SEM) (Huck, 2012).

CFA begins by determining the theoretically possible indicators behind the unmeasured dimensions of students' statistical disposition. In SEM, it is hypothesised that the theoretical model of students' statistical disposition consists of 29 indicators or observed variables or manifest variables (Huck, 2012). Data on manifest variables were collected from undergraduate, postgraduate, and doctoral students at the last meeting of the statistics lecture they attended using an 11-point rating scale. From the CFA results, it is known that there are seven models of dimensions and indicators of students' statistical disposition. The initial models are theoretical models of students' statistical disposition dimensions and indicators.

A summary of the model fit index and indicators eliminated to obtain a better model is presented in Table 8.

Table 8: Summary of Model Fit Index Dimensions and Indicators Students’ Statistical Disposition

No.	Model Fit Index	Condition	Model						
			Initial	1	2	3	4	5	6
1	Chi Square	(Hair et al., 2013)	785.323	606.790	349.614	263.664	115.030	86.872	55.749
2	Df		356	278	168	120	75	67	50
3	Probability	≥ 0.05 (Hair et al., 2013)	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.002	0.002	0.268
4	Cmin/df	≤ 2.00 (Schermelel-Engel et al., 2003)	2.206	2.183	2.081	2.197	1.534	1.401	1.115
5	RMSEA	≤ 0.08 (Schermelel-Engel et al., 2003)	0.098	0.097	0.093	0.098	0.065	0.057	0.030
6	GFI	≥ 0.90 (Schermelel-Engel et al., 2003)	0.643	0.736	0.801	0.823	0.894	0.910	0.939
7	TLI	≥ 0.90 (Schermelel-Engel et al., 2003)	0.841	0.867	0.904	0.912	0.967	0.977	0.994
8	CFI	≥ 0.95 (Schermelel-Engel et al., 2003)	0.861	0.886	0.923	0.931	0.976	0.984	0.996
Conclusion			Model is not fit	Model is not fit	Model is not fit	Model is not fit	Model is not fit	Model is not fit	Model is not fit
Indicators that are eliminated from the model to obtain the next model			X ₁₂ , X ₁₄ , X ₆₁	X ₁₅ , X ₂₅ , X ₁₃ , X ₆₂ , X ₄₆	X ₁₁ , X ₆₃ , X ₁₆	X ₄₅ , X ₅₃ , X ₂₄	X ₂₂	X ₄₄	

From Table 8, it is evident that the initial model cannot be used to model students’ statistical disposition dimensions and indicators, as the six model fit indices (Hair et al., 2013; Schermelleh-Engel et al., 2003) are not satisfied. This means that the theoretical model of students’ statistical disposition, comprising seven dimensions and 29 indicators, cannot be used. Therefore, modifications were made to the Initial Model by eliminating indicators with loadings <0.7 (Hair et al., 2013) and simultaneously evaluating the six fit indices (Huck, 2012) determined above.

Modification of the initial model was carried out by eliminating three manifesters (indicators), namely: punctual attendance in lectures (X₁₂), collecting assignments (X₁₄), and the desire to solve new challenging problems (X₆₁), so that Model-1 of students’ statistical disposition consisting of seven indicators and twenty-six indicators was obtained.

From the Model-1 fit test results, it is known that the six model fit indices are not satisfied so they must be modified. Modification of Model-1 is done by eliminating five manifest variables (indicators) that have the smallest factor loading (Huck, 2012) namely: the desire to do assignments (X_{13}), activeness in attending lectures (X_{15}), confidence in using statistics (X_{25}), persistence in understanding other important aspects of statistics (X_{46}), and the desire to learn the material to be lectured (X_{62}) from Model-1 so that Model-2 is obtained which consists of seven indicators and twenty-one indicators.

From the fit test results of Model-2, it is known that the six fit indices are close to the specified limits but have not been satisfied. Therefore, Model-2 was modified by eliminating three manifest variables (indicators) that had the smallest factor loading (Huck, 2012), namely: interest in lectures (X_{11}), seriousness in attending lectures (X_{16}), and the desire to have other reading sources besides those required by lecturers (X_{63}) from Model-2 to obtain Model-3 which consists of six dimensions and eighteen indicators.

From the fit test results for Model-3, the six fit indices are close to the specified limits but have not been satisfied. Therefore, Model-3 was modified by eliminating three manifest variables (indicators) that had the smallest factor loading (Huck, 2012), namely: confidence in solving problems (X_{24}), persistence in understanding concepts (X_{45}), and willingness to respond to other people's ideas and statistical thinking based on one's own thinking (X_{53}) from Model-3 to obtain Model-4 which consists of six indicators and fifteen indicators.

From the Model-4 fit test results, it is known that there are still two of the six model fit indices that have not been satisfied so they must be modified. Model-4 modification is done by eliminating two manifest variables (indicators) that have the smallest factor loading (Huck, 2012), namely: confidence in asking questions (X_{21}), and confidence in answering questions (X_{22}), from Model-4 to obtain Model-5, which consists of six indicators and fourteen indicators.

From the results of the Model-5 fit test, it is evident that one of the six model fit indices has not been satisfied, so Model-5 must be modified. Model-5 is modified by eliminating the manifest variable (indicator) with the smallest factor loading (Huck, 2012), namely, persistence in understanding procedures (X_{44}), resulting in Model-6, which consists of six indicators and thirteen indicators. The test results show that Model-6 has satisfied all six-dimensional model fit indices and students' statistical disposition indicators.

Research Limitations

This study acknowledges several limitations that warrant consideration in interpreting the findings. The sample size remains limited for robust generalisation to the broader population of Indonesian higher education students, and the sampling was restricted to students from select universities within specific regions, potentially limiting the representativeness of findings across the diverse landscape of Indonesian higher education institutions. Institutional characteristics such as university status (public vs. private), accreditation levels, geographical location, students' socioeconomic backgrounds, and statistical instruction quality may influence students' statistical disposition but were not fully represented in the current sample. Additionally, the cross-sectional

design captured statistical disposition at a single time point and relied on self-report measures, which may be subject to response bias. These limitations affect the generalizability of the findings, as results may not be directly applicable to the entire Indonesian student population without further validation, and the developed model may require adjustments across different institutional or disciplinary contexts. Future research should therefore replicate this study with larger, more diverse samples from various universities that represent the breadth of Indonesian higher education institutions, including students from different academic disciplines and educational levels, and employ longitudinal designs to examine changes in statistical disposition over time. Through such replication and expansion efforts, the construct validity and generalizability of the multidimensional model of students' statistical disposition can be confirmed and strengthened, thereby providing more significant contributions to the development of statistical education in Indonesia.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Based on the theoretical study results, this research developed an instrument to measure students' statistical disposition. The instrument developed is a rating scale consisting of seven dimensions and twenty-nine indicators. The rating scale used is an 11-point scale arranged sequentially from left to right, starting from point 0 to 10. The validity test results show that all (29) of the rating scales developed are valid and reliable at the $\alpha = 5\%$ significance level.

The EFA results, using KMO and Bartlett's test, indicated that the sample size in this study met the sample adequacy requirements. Furthermore, from the Anti-image Correlation and Extraction Communalities values, it is evident that the seven dimensions and twenty-nine indicators can be included in the theoretical model (an ideal category initial model) of the dimensions and indicators of students' statistical disposition, which will be further analysed using CFA.

The CFA results using six model fit indices, namely Probability, Cmin/df, RMSEA, GFI, TLI, and CGI, showed that the Initial Model (Figure 1), containing seven dimensions and twenty-nine indicators, did not meet the six model fit indices. Therefore, the original model cannot be used and must be modified. After six modifications and gradual model testing, Model-6 (Figure 6) was finally obtained, which fulfilled all six model fit indices of students' statistical disposition dimensions and indicators. This final model, referred to as the empirically validated model of students' statistical disposition dimensions and indicators, is shown in Figure 7.

The empirical construction results show that students' statistical disposition has six dimensions and thirteen indicators, namely: 1) Self-confidence, indicators: confidence in asking questions, and confidence in communicating ideas; 2) Flexibility in exploring ideas and alternative problem solving, indicators: flexibility in exploring statistical ideas, and flexibility in finding alternative solutions to statistical problems; 3) Persistence in facing and solving problems. indicators: persistence in facing statistical problems, persistence in solving statistical problems, and persistence in understanding problems; 4) Monitoring and reflecting on thinking. Indicators: the ability to pay attention to ideas and statistical thinking put forward by lecturers and or students,

and the ability to pay attention to ideas and statistical thinking put forward by students; 5) High curiosity. Indicators: the desire to learn non-routine things, and the desire to ask non-routine things; 6) Sharing opinions with others. Indicators: the desire to share opinions, ideas, and ideas with lecturers, and the desire to share opinions, ideas, and ideas with fellow students.

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